

1 *Supporting information for the paper*

2 *Biogeography of bird and mammal trophic structures*

3
4 *Multidimensional space exploration with 'AMD analysis'*

5 In 'hard' clustering, data are divided into distinct clusters, whereby each element belongs
6 to one cluster. In fuzzy or 'soft' clustering, elements being clustered show degrees of
7 membership to each cluster (a value between 0 and 1 linked to the squared Euclidean
8 distance to the geometric center of the cluster). Most measurements of cluster validity
9 quantify the degree of cluster separation (measuring how distinct clusters are from each
10 other) and the compactness (measuring how internally consistent they are) (e.g., Davies-
11 Bouldin or Dunn Indexes). Clusters whose elements show a high degree of membership
12 can be then considered well-defined, or internally consistent, whereas clusters with many
13 elements with unclear membership can be considered diffuse or fuzzy.

14
15 Suppose that a set of elements are distributed in an n -dimensional space (defined by n
16 variables) forming c relatively well-defined clusters. If the number of clusters c' selected
17 are smaller than the number of clusters that actually exist in the data ($c' < c$), two or more
18 clusters, no matter how different and separated they are, will be forced to be included in
19 the same cluster. The average Euclidean distance of the elements of that cluster to the
20 geometric center will be greater than that of clusters that would include them separately.
21 Therefore, both the degree of membership of its elements to that cluster and its average
22 membership degree (AMD) will be lower. If the number of clusters selected is, on the
23 contrary, higher ($c' > c$), one or more clusters, no matter how well-defined they are, will
24 be divided into different clusters, thus also reducing their AMD value. When clusters are
25 more separated (distinct) and more compact (well-defined), it is when a number of

26 clusters equal to the number of groups that actually exist in the data is selected ($c' = c$).
27 This is also when AMD takes its maximum value.

28

29 This relationship between the number of clusters that actually exist in the data and the
30 number of clusters selected allowed us to develop an index based on the AMD of the
31 elements composing the clusters, and asking whether a set of elements distributed in n -
32 dimensional space form relatively well-defined groups and, if so, how many groups they
33 are:

$$34 \quad AMD_i = (1/n \sum_{j=1}^{j=n} MD_j) - 1/c$$

35 where MD_j is the degree of membership of sample j to the nearest cluster, n the number
36 of samples and c the number of clusters.

37

38 *Step 1. Obtaining the AMDi curve*

39 The curve tracking the AMD_i values through a series of clustering analysis runs with an
40 increasing number of user-defined clusters (referred from now as ‘ AMD_i curve’) allows
41 to test whether a set of samples, located in a multidimensional space, are randomly
42 distributed or form clusters departing from random chance. The existence of clusters is
43 revealed by the existence of a maximum peak in the AMD_i curve, when the number of
44 user-defined clusters matches the number of clusters that actually exist in the set of
45 samples.

46

47 *Step 2. Obtaining a comparison frame*

48 Once the number of clusters is known, it is possible to obtain an average estimate of
49 their degree of definition, based on the maximum value reached by the peak of the

50 AMDi curve and its sharpness. To do this, it is first necessary to generate comparison
51 patterns with sets of artificial samples, forming clusters with different degrees of
52 definition (user-controlled by their standard deviation). When the samples are generated
53 by randomly distributing them (they do not form clusters), the resulting AMDi curve is
54 flat. When the samples are generated forming clusters (with varying standard
55 deviations), both the maximum AMDi value and the sharpness of the peak indicate how
56 well defined the clusters were generated. The higher the standard deviation, the greater
57 their dispersion and, therefore, the lower their definition. The larger the definition of the
58 groups (lower standard deviation), the higher and sharper is the resulting peak
59 indicating the number of groups. For the clusters in our sample set to be fully
60 comparable with the artificial sets, the number of samples in both sets must be the same
61 or similar and both the number of dimensions of the space in which they are located and
62 the number of clusters they form must be the same.

63

64 This analysis, referred as ‘AMD analysis’, was applied to the 9-dimensional
65 community-level trophic space, in which, according to our first prediction, samples
66 should not be distributed continuously, rather forming discrete groups (see main text).

67

68 *Identification of trophic guilds*

69 Although our predictions do not refer to the distribution of species in the space defined
70 by the estimated consumption of resources, we applied the first step of the AMD
71 analysis to the species-level trophic space. The AMDi curve obtained does not show a
72 peak (Fig. 2f), which is an indication they do not form well-defined clusters; hence we
73 did not compare this curve with curves generated with artificial samples (second step of
74 the AMD analysis). However, they are also not randomly distributed, like the artificial

75 samples of figure 2a, since the AMD_i value increases from 2 to 9 user-defined clusters
76 (Fig. 2f). From 9 user-defined clusters, AMD_i does not decrease but it oscillates, which
77 can be interpreted as indicating the existence of 9 groups made up of smaller groups.
78 We lack an explanation for this pattern. Because our analysis is global and the focus is
79 on generality, we selected the nine major trophic guilds given that they are more likely
80 to be shared across biogeographical realms (Fig. 1).

81

82 *Identification of community trophic structures*

83 Our first prediction is that communities, even if continuously distributed in a
84 geographical space, will not be continuously distributed in the ‘community-level trophic
85 space’, rather forming well-defined groups separated by empty or sparsely populated
86 regions. The AMD_i curve (first step of the AMD analysis) was obtained for the
87 community-level trophic space, which allowed us to test for the presence of clusters, as
88 well as their number. To estimate their degree of definition, four sets of artificial
89 samples were generated (second step of the AMD analysis), using the same number of
90 samples (18418) and dimensions (9) as the community-level trophic space. With the
91 first set, consisting of randomly distributed samples (they do not form clusters), the
92 resulting AMD_i curve is flat (Fig. 2a). The other three sets of artificial clusters were
93 generated forming six clusters with increasing values of standard deviation (5, 10 and
94 15, in a 100-sided space), implying progressively lower degrees of group definition. As
95 expected, the AMD_i curve reached the maximum value when the user-defined number
96 of clusters was equal to the number of groups that actually exist in the data (six, in this
97 case). In addition, the larger the definition of the groups (lower standard deviation), the
98 higher and sharper was the resulting peak indicating the number of groups (Figs. 2b, 2c,
99 2d). The AMD_i curves obtained with these four sets of artificial samples were used as

100 standards of comparison with which to estimate the degree of definition of the clusters

101 identified in the community-level trophic space.

102

103 DOI for data and code is [doi:10.5061/dryad.nk98sf7st](https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.nk98sf7st).